

Public Involvement and Engagement Working Group: March 2024

Executive summary

Stakeholders across data science, healthcare research, patient and public engagement and involvement, and public representatives convened to address the need to improve representativeness in health data research. Participants identified several challenges, including the predominance of research initiatives in England which often neglects the unique needs of other UK regions, leading to unrepresentative data. Communication barriers also persist, as data science is frequently communicated in technical language inaccessible to the general public, despite the average reading age in the UK being nine years old. Historical mistreatment of minoritised groups and socio-economic disparities continue to hinder trust and participation in health research, compounded by inconsistent data definitions across jurisdictions and insufficient funding that limits effective community engagement.

To improve data representativeness, the discussions highlighted the need for standardising data collection across the UK to ensure comprehensive and comparable data. Enhanced community engagement strategies such as stakeholder mapping and partnerships with local organisations are crucial for reaching and accurately representing underserved populations. Additionally, adapting communication strategies to be understandable across all educational levels and transparently informing participants about the use of their data are essential for enhancing participation and building trust.

The potential of the PEDRI-Alliance partnership was underlined as a means to facilitate resource sharing, fostering collaborations, and developing shared resources.

Challenges	Good practice	Suggestions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regional differences and disparities • Communicating data science to diverse audiences • Mistrust • Limited resources for engagement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Partnerships to mitigate resource limitation • Proactive transparency • Targeted communication and engagement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Resource sharing • Capacity building • Fostering collaboration

Introduction

This was the third in a series of meetings of a new Public Involvement and Engagement working group, convened by the [Alliance](#) in partnership with [PEDRI](#) (Public Engagement in Data Research Initiative). This series of events, aims to provide an opportunity to discuss public involvement and engagement priorities of Alliance members and partner organisations, explore ways to reduce complexities and drive adoption of best practice in public engagement and involvement, and gain insight into PEDRI's strategic objectives.

The UK Health Data Research Alliance (the 'Alliance') is an independent alliance of leading healthcare and research organisations united to establish best practice for the ethical use of UK health data for research at scale.

The PEDRI initiative builds on a sector-wide desire to share learning, best practice, and collaborate on public involvement and engagement (PIE) in data-driven research and statistics. PEDRI was officially launched on 19th October 2022 as a partnership between Administrative Data Research UK (ADR UK), Data and Analytics Research Environments UK (DARE UK), Health Data Research UK (HDR UK), NHS Transformation Directorate (NHS TD), Research Data Scotland, and Office for National Statistics (ONS).

PEDRI has recently received funding from [DARE UK](#) and is a formal [DARE UK community group](#). As part of this, PEDRI is forging a strategic partnership with the Alliance. This partnership marks a significant step towards achieving our shared goals in data research and enhancing the impact we can make in our community. The Alliance's wealth of expertise and resources will complement PEDRI's mission and initiatives.

Workshop participation

The workshop was held online over Zoom on the 13th of March 2024. 43 attendees participated in the workshop. A list of participating organisations can be found in the appendix at the end of this document.

Workshop outputs

There were four outputs from the workshop:

1. Presentations by speakers
2. Discussing ways of improving representation in data
3. Discussion on the current practice of Public Involvement and Engagement (PIE) in health research
4. Suggestions from the community on focus areas for future workshops

1. Presentations

The workshop had two presentations by the speakers.

- 1. Diabetes Research Centre and Centre for Ethnic Health Research (University of Leicester)**
 - The presentation focused on the changing demographics in the UK, particularly the increase in ethnic diversity. This shift underscores the need for health data systems to adapt and adequately reflect these changes.
 - There are challenges in collecting accurate and representative data from ethnic minorities and other underrepresented groups. There is a need to overcome these challenges to address health inequalities effectively.
 - The presentation discussed strategies employed by the Centre for Ethnic Health Research to enhance data collection and community engagement. This includes building trust with communities through sustained outreach and adapting research methodologies to be more inclusive.

- 2. Planetary Health Informatics (PHI) Lab (University of Oxford)**
 - Planetary Health Informatics Lab initiated a campaign titled "*Be Proud to Reveal Your Ethnicity.*" This campaign aims to encourage patients to provide their ethnicity data, which is critical for improving care and research outcomes.
 - As part of the campaign, multilingual resources were developed to facilitate understanding and participation across different language-speaking groups.
 - The campaign seeks to enhance the quality of health research by ensuring that data on ethnicity are more complete and representative. This is particularly important for tailoring health interventions and policies to diverse populations.

The presentations were followed by Q&A sessions. The links to the presentations can be found in the appendix section at the end of this document.

2. Improving representation in data

Ensuring representativeness in data is crucial for producing reliable insights and making informed decisions that accurately reflect the realities of the population being studied. In the breakout rooms, attendees discussed how the data and statistics community could improve representation in data. The feedback was generated around three broad questions:

1. What organisations are currently doing to improve the representativeness of data in their organisation.
2. What is considered good practice.
3. What can be achieved by the PEDRI-Alliance partnership to improve representativeness.

Challenges to improving representativeness in data

1. Regional differences in health data research

- The predominance of England in initiatives often overshadows research needs and projects in other regions, such as Scotland and Wales. This leads to data that does not universally represent the UK.
- There are issues with missing data and inconsistencies due to different regulatory practices in the Four Nations

“...Northern Ireland data isn't included in studies and that always concerns me”

2. Communicating data science to diverse audiences

- Researchers often fail to engage effectively with the public, unaware of the diverse levels of understanding about data science.
- The average reading age in the UK is 9, yet data science communication remains technical and inaccessible to many.
- There is a significant lack of research on barriers to engagement and involvement in health research among different socio-economic groups.

“I didn't know Scotland weren't required to record ethnicity data”

3. Mistrust in data science research:

- Historical wrongdoings in medical research involving minoritised ethnic groups have left a legacy of distrust.
- Socio-economic disparities also influence trust and engagement levels with health research.

4. Differences in categorising and defining data

- Variations in how data is defined within jurisdictions, such as differences between biological sex and gender, can complicate data collection and analysis.

5. Limited resources

- Inadequate funding restricts the ability to build relationships and engage with communities, filling data gaps and enhancing research inclusivity.
- Resource disparity in research in the Four Nations hamper efforts for extensive engagement across demographics and geographies.

Ways to improve representation in health data research

1. Cross nation research:

- Implement uniform data collection standards across the UK to ensure comprehensive data.
- Facilitate comparability and enhance the reliability of research findings.

2. Employing diverse and targeted means of community engagement:

- Use equality impact assessments and stakeholder mapping at macro, meso, and micro levels to understand community needs.
- Partner with local community organisations to reach underserved populations to ensure their voices are heard in research.
- Acknowledge the importance of underserved geographies like rural areas, in addition to underserved demographic groups in research.
- Explore and develop concrete mechanisms that reflect the needs and experiences of all segments of the population.

“...we acknowledged the role that academia and medicine played in incredibly despicable behaviour towards minoritised ethnic groups in order for medical and research gains...we got the video translated into different languages and played it at every one of the focus groups that we went to because we wanted to start by acknowledging that we were in the wrong...”

3. Improving Communication Strategies

- Reduce participation bias by making research communication understandable to people at all educational levels, for example, by using visual aids, videos and simple summaries.

4. Proactive transparency about data use

- Inform patients and research participants about the use of their data for research through multiple platforms, and provide easy opt-out options, enhancing trust and transparency.

5. Collaborative Projects and Partnerships

- Combine forces through joint initiatives between organisations to mitigate issues in resource allocation and expertise.

Suggestions for PEDRI-Alliance partnership

1. Resource sharing:

- The partnership can help with facilitating projects that may otherwise be unfeasible due to financial constraints.
- Non-financial resources like help to develop communication tools for non-English speaking audiences can be shared through the partnership.

2. Fostering linkages and partnerships:

- Initiate joint projects leveraging PEDRI-Alliance’s network in health and data research.
- Enhance project outcomes through diverse participant involvement and collaborative expertise.

3. Capacity building:

- Develop shared training programs to enhance partner capabilities in developing and managing projects in health and data research.
- Create a resource pool for engagement and inclusive data involvement practices.

Initiatives by organisations to improve representativeness in health data research

Issue	Organisation	Detail
Cultural competency for community engagement in health data research	Centre for Ethnic Health Research, University of Leicester	Offers training to increase knowledge and confidence in engaging with ethnic communities, as well as to become more culturally competent
Improving data quality and representativeness	Planetary Health Informatics Lab, University of Oxford	<p><i>Be Proud to Reveal Your Ethnicity</i> campaign encouraged patients to provide ethnicity data to enhance care and research outcomes, accompanied by multilingual resources.</p> <p>More information here: Project Patient and Public Involvement – Nuffield Department of Orthopaedics, Rheumatology and Musculoskeletal Sciences (ox.ac.uk)</p>
Data Accessibility and Use Transparency	Moorfields Eye Hospital	Inform patients about the automatic collection and use of their health data for research, aiming to increase transparency and trust.

<p>Historical distrust</p>	<p>University of Edinburgh and Queen’s Mary University, London</p>	<p><i>INCLUDED</i> project acknowledged mistakes made in the past by researchers before engaging with people from minoritised ethnic groups. More detail here: - Queen Mary University of London (qmul.ac.uk) Video here: INCLUDED Focus Group Video (youtube.com)</p>
<p>Community engagement</p>	<p>Various, including West Midlands Secure Data Environments in partnership with University of Birminham</p>	<p>Stakeholder mapping, Equality Impact Assessment, and engagement at micro (ward) levels</p>
<p>Patient’s experience of participating in research</p>	<p>NIHR Research Network</p>	<p>Produces an annual report that records patient’s experience. The report also has information about demographic characteristics of those involved in research. Find latest report here: Participant in Research Experience Survey (PRES) NIHR</p>
<p>Diversity in data science</p>	<p>Health Data Research UK</p>	<p><i>Black Internship Programme</i> supports the career progression of underrepresented groups in data science, focusing particularly on Black students pursuing data science degrees in UK universities.</p>

3. Discussion: addressing current practice

1. Measuring impact

- When measuring impact there needs to be a standardised way of showing benefits to patients who participate in research. A classification system that records patient benefits as an end outcome needs to be in place, and more work needs to be done around patient-reported outcomes.
- Impact must also include public benefit.
- Developing an impact measure of patient and public benefit should be done in consultation with a diverse range of stakeholders.

“What is the benefit for that patient, whether it's a form of chemo or a new dressing?”

2. Digital exclusion

- Whilst “Zoom has been a boon” for some, it is not appropriate for everyone, and should not be the default way of engaging with stakeholders and the public.
- Relying on digital medium of engagement can result in an echo chamber and exclude “the man on the street”

“...trust is a big barrier for collecting data, and there's two views-public view and patient view. And they need to be addressed separately and you need to talk to them separately...”

4. Suggestions for future workshops

1.	Public’s attitudes to data sharing
2.	Discussing approaches where the nature of research being undertaken may limit the to be co-productive throughout a research cycle, for example in technical data analysis.
3.	Commercialisation and it’s impact on public involvement in data research.
4.	AI and public trust in involvement

5. Conclusion and next steps

The three PEDRI-Alliance workshops brought together partners and stakeholders working across the health and non-health data and research ecosystems, including NHS bodies, academic institutions, and public representatives. The workshops not only provided insights into key PEDRI workstreams like the Good Practice Standards, but also informed our future work. We heard what both PIE professionals and the public consider important themes for discussion, including data privacy, EDI, ethical considerations, and innovative research methodologies. These workshops have proven to be invaluable in fostering collaboration, driving forward-thinking conversations, and setting a clear direction for future initiatives. Continuing these workshops will ensure that we remain at the forefront of addressing critical issues and evolving needs in the health data and research landscape.

Appendix

Jam-board

FEEDBACK ON CURRENT PRACTICE: WHAT THEY ARE DOING AND WHAT WORKS

SUGGESTIONS: WHAT CAN PEDRI-ALLIANCE PARTNERSHIP ACHIEVE

Agenda

Chairs: Doreen Tembo (HDR UK) and Paola Quattroni (Alliance)

Date: 13.3.2024

Time: 13:00-14:30

Speakers: Cameron Razieh, Krishna Patel (University of Leicester), Amelia Doran (University of Oxford)

Time	Session	Chair
5 mins	Introduction	Paola Quattroni
15 mins	Under-represented groups in health research	Cameron Razieh and Krishna Patel
10 mins	Ethnicity, Equity and AI	Amelia Doran
20 mins	Breakout session: How can this community of practice improve representation in data?	
Break (5 mins)		
5 mins	Alliance and PEDRI's strategic plans (2023-2028)	Doreen Tembo
20 mins	Open session: Where do we go from here?	Doreen Tembo
5 mins	Wrap-up and thanks	Doreen Tembo

Presentations

Doreen Tembo: <https://ukhealthdata.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/07/Doreen-Tembo-presentation-March-2024-PEDRI-Alliance-Workshop.pdf>

University of Leicester: <https://ukhealthdata.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/07/University-of-Leicester-CEHR-presentation-March-2024-PEDRI-Alliance-workshop.pdf>

University of Oxford: <https://ukhealthdata.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/07/University-of-Oxford-NDORMS-presentation-March-2024-PEDRI-Alliance-workshop.pdf>

Participating organisations and hubs

- Clinical Practice Research Datalink
- Understanding Patient Data
- Cancer Research UK
- Use MY Data
- University of Leicester
- University of Oxford
- University of Edinburgh
- Office for Statistics Regulation
- Health Data Research UK Wales
- Data and Analytics Research Environment UK
- Intensive Care National Audit & Research Centre
- NIHR Clinical Research Network (CRNCC)
- Swansea University
- Health Data Research UK Public Advisory Board
- Health Data Research UK Social and Environmental Determinants of Health Driver Programme
- BHF Data Science Centre
- Research Data Scotland
- Administrative Data Research, Wales
- INSIGHT Health Data Research Hub

Contact us

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